
The new charter of the administrative deconcentrating a lever of the advanced regionalization in Morocco.

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Abstract

The objective of this article is based first of all on a thematic reason, since the new charter of administrative deconcentrating is in the continuity of the great construction site of advanced regionalization that Morocco knows, it is a multiform strategic orientation arousing a particular interest among researchers in the field of political science, governance, among other disciplines. Indeed, the advanced regionalization project constitutes a configuration that is composed of a plethora of parameters, the pillar of which is ineluctably administrative deconcentrating. It is important to analyse it, in view of the importance of the modes of governance of the State. This research addresses various aspects, of a technical, practical, procedural, and economic nature. Our objective is to demonstrate what administrative deconcentrating consists of in Morocco, and what are its illustrations? And this by a study which allows to highlight the convergence between the new charter of administrative deconcentrating, in relation to the various actors.

Keywords: administrative deconcentrating, advanced regionalization, governance, delegation

Introduction

The administrative organization of unitary states varies between two main modalities, namely centralization and decentralization. Decentralization is also a system of administrative organization that consists of handing over important decision-making powers in broad areas to local agents distributed throughout the national territory and linked to the central power by a hierarchical level. First of all, it makes it possible to relieve the central power and to obtain decisions that are better elaborated and better adapted to local requirements. It is up to the local representatives of the central power to decide themselves on the spot, the questions that arise at the local level without them being obliged to wait for the decision that must come from the top, and in order to have a more rational decision-making process since the local agents are installed on the spot. This allows them to make decisions based on local needs. In Morocco, the advanced regionalization model, built around deconcentrating and administrative decentralization, is a strategic choice that reveals a global vision of development and territorial governance. A new impetus was given to this project by the Royal Appeal for the government to draw up a charter for administrative deconcentrating. Such a charter, followed by all the desired effect in practice, should provide advanced regionalization with essential support: that of placing opposite the regional councils and the councils of the other territorial authorities state administrations that have, at each of these levels, real margins of initiative and effective decision-making powers, while being effectively coordinated and synergized, in the service of integrated development and as close as possible to the populations concerned and the elected representatives. The decentralization process initiated in Morocco since independence seems to be gaining momentum in recent years. Indeed, the various reforms carried out over the last decade suggest a shift from an essentially security-based vision of the territory (the region) to one where the latter is considered a major player in the implementation and design of development policies. In this context, the elaboration of the charter of administrative deconcentrating constitutes a pillar of the process of advanced regionalization in Morocco by providing regional and sub-regional deconcentrated services with real margins of initiative and decision-making power, something that depends largely on effective coordination¹.

The Moroccan administrative organization includes two basic systems, that of the unicity of the administrative authority, better known as "administrative centralization" and the system of multi-authorities, called "administrative deconcentrating". Faced with the evolutions and

¹ Abdallah HARSI, Decentralization and administrative deconcentration: Instruments of administrative proximity, Maghrebien symposium on : "L'administration de proximité: concept et implications" organized by REMALD and the Ecole Nationale de l'Administration, with the support of the Hanss Seidel Foundation, on Thursday 24 and Friday 25 November 2005 at the headquarters of ENA, Rabat.

transformations that Morocco has experienced and accumulated, in terms of administrative history on the one hand and the needs and demands of citizens on the other, the Moroccan administration is now trying to combine speed with performance and quality of services. Administrative deconcentrating has become the management mode adapted to achieve efficiency, rationalization and speed in the administrative exercise, through the distribution of prerogatives between the central and territorial administrative authority. In all this, the role of the region will serve as a basis for the general perception of administrative deconcentrating because it is the territorial level whose jurisdiction is most likely to apply national policies in various areas such as economic and social development and land administration. The pillars of decentralization cannot be established in the absence of a clear strategy of administrative deconcentrating, which is considered an essential precondition for territorial decentralization. In fact, research shows that the two concepts are complementary, and supports the role of deconcentrating, which offers prospects for territorial development. This charter was developed on the basis of and following the Royal Directives addressed to the government in order to accompany the process of advanced regionalization, and to provide the necessary conditions for the implementation of the State's public policies at the territorial level. This is in addition to the pivotal role of the Walis of the regions as representatives of the central authority at the regional level, ensuring the coordination of the activities of the decentralized services, and ensuring the proper functioning and monitoring of their activities, Obviously, the importance of the subject is not to be demonstrated, it lies in understanding the differences between deconcentrating and other perceptions of the administration, whether central or decentralized and not to sink into confusion. In addition, it is important to be able to know the different prerogatives of the stakeholders, in particular the Walis and Governors, among other actors of the administration. Also, the National Charter of Administrative deconcentrating establishes new modes of governance and modernizes the architecture of the State administration. This article is therefore an opportunity to highlight the convergence between the new administrative deconcentrating charter and the different actors in Morocco, with the aim of answering the problem of the study, which is formulated as follows: what does administrative deconcentrating consist of in Morocco and what are its illustrations?

To answer this question, we adopted a descriptive methodology based on documentary research. Therefore, we have adopted a plan that will be structured in two topics:

1. In the first topic we start with the concept of administrative deconcentrating.
2. Then, the analysis of the new coordination mechanisms according to the new charter of administrative deconcentrating in Morocco.

1. The concept of administrative deconcentrating

The new charter of administrative deconcentrating a lever for advanced regionalisation in Morocco, the deconcentrating of the administration aims at a better deployment of the State's public policies and a better quality of public services on the territory by transferring the power of decision and the means of action from the centre to the territory and taking decisions as close as possible to the user with speed, quality and the best cost for the community. This is a modern mode of administrative governance whose concern is to raise the efficiency of public policies to the highest level, to improve the quality of public service and to facilitate users' access to all essential services and social welfare. In the practice of the Moroccan administration, objective factors related to the size of the territory and the insufficiency of human and financial resources justified for a good period and until the beginning of the 1990s, the limitation of this movement to an organic and geographical deconcentrating of the administration. This movement, which was necessary but not sufficient, was extended over the years to the detriment of the deconcentrating of decision-making powers, the scope of which remained very limited and almost confined to the area of sub-financing of expenditure and the supervision of rural communes entrusted to the Governors. The 1976 communal charter and the pressure of elected representatives, who were increasingly demanding more operational external services from the administration, led to the drafting of a decree in 1993 which remained a dead letter because it had its own limitations. It provided for a truncated deconcentrating by devolving decision-making power exclusively in the form of a simple delegation of signature, and in fact marks the lack of enthusiasm of the central political power to undertake this reform under various and unconvincing pretexts, notably by brandishing the lack of means and the lack of competence of the external services, whereas the real reason resided rather in the desire to put the administration in the hands of the authorities. In 2002, this reform was put on hold because of its complexity and especially because of its supposed impact on the erosion of the government's central power.

The year 2002 will see a very strong Royal impulse through the deconcentrating of competences related to the act of investing and creating companies, entrusted to a single window concretised by the creation of regional investment centres (RIC) directed by senior executives benefiting from the status of central director and the devolution of decision-making powers to the regional Walis in substitution of powers previously held by the Prime Minister and the Ministers concerned by the transfer of these powers. This transfer of decision-making powers was duly enshrined in the relevant regulatory texts and has had undeniable repercussions, particularly in

terms of proximity, simplification of procedures, transparency and shortening of the administration's response time. The year 2005 also saw the advent of the National Initiative for Human Development (INDH) which, under a new Royal impetus, constituted an original experience in terms of deconcentrating, territorialisation of approaches, and the introduction of participatory approaches. The integrated social development actions initiated within the framework of this project aimed to implement projects with an immediate and targeted impact for the benefit of marginalised and vulnerable populations in the most remote and marginalised areas of the country and in poor urban neighbourhoods. It is also a pioneering experiment in simplifying expenditure procedures and deconcentrating the budget. Attempts by the executive in 1993 and 2005 respectively (decree 2-93-625 of 20/10/1993 and decree 2-05-1369 of 21/12/2005) to initiate deconcentrating unfortunately met with the same fate, which was failure. The same conceptual inadequacies centred on the delegation of signature and the multiplication of external services with no real decision-making power, reveal a lack of global vision and firm political will to engage in true deconcentrating which. The same conceptual shortcomings based on the delegation of signature and the multiplication of external services without real decision-making power reveal a lack of global vision and a firm political will to engage in a real deconcentrating that "beats in the face" the vertical and centralising approach of the Administration decried by all.

1.1. *The foundations of the New Deconcentrating Charter*

The policy of administrative deconcentrating is based on the following two main foundations

- The region as an appropriate territorial space for the realization of the national policy of administrative deconcentrating, given the pre-eminent position it occupies in the administrative organization of the Kingdom, which makes it an intermediary level in the relations between the central administrations of the State and their representations at the territorial level;
- The central role of the Wali of the region, in his capacity as representative of the central power at the regional level, in the coordination of the activities of the deconcentrated services of the State by ensuring their proper functioning and control, under the authority of the concerned ministers, in order to achieve the efficiency, effectiveness and convergence necessary for the implementation and monitoring of public policies at the regional level².

² Article 5 of Decree No. 2-17-618 on the national charter for administrative deconcentrating.

1.2. The principles of administrative deconcentrating

The principles of administrative deconcentrating, the pillar of advanced regionalization, can be summarized as follows:

- Equitable coverage of the national territory by ensuring a fair geographical distribution of the deconcentrated services of the State;
- Subsidiarity in the distribution of missions and the determination of attributions between the central administrations and the decentralized services that come under them;
- The pre-eminent position of the region in the territorial administrative organization as an intermediate level in the organization of relations between the central level and the other territorial levels;
- The consecration of the central role of the Wali of the region in the coordination of the action of the deconcentrated services of the State, by ensuring their good functioning and their control, in order to ensure the effectiveness and the efficiency in the exercise of their missions;
- The unity of action of the deconcentrated services of the State in order to ensure the efficiency, effectiveness, convergence and complementarity of the attributions which are devolved to them, while applying the principle of correlation between the responsibility and the accountability in the evaluation of their action;
- The simplification of procedures for access to public services and their popularization among users, by assisting them in the accomplishment of these procedures in the appropriate conditions;
- Bringing public services closer to users, promoting them and guaranteeing their quality and continuity;
- The matching of the transfer of competences to the deconcentrated services with the allocation of financial and human resources to the said services, in order to enable them to carry out the missions and attributions entrusted to them;
- The principles of competence, merit and equal opportunity in the appointment of officials responsible for the management of the deconcentrated services;

Advanced regionalization, a real institutional and governance revolution, with its scope, ambitions, challenges and diverse and multiform reform implications on all aspects of the exercise of power and the sharing of resources both at the level of the State and the local authorities³.

³ Requirements of advanced regionalization and challenges of sectoral policy integration, report of the Economic, Social and Environmental Council; Auto saisine n°22/2016.

The region is considered to be the core of the administrative, as it was imposed from the first years of independence as a necessary imperative for the state to assume its new responsibilities related to the achievement of economic and social development. The role of administrative deconcentrating in the elevation of advanced regionalization requires making the region a space and a framework for administrative deconcentrating.

1.2.1. The distribution of responsibilities between the central administrations and the decentralized services of the State

The new charter has clearly underlined that the central administrations deal with the missions that represent, according to the texts in force, a national character or that cannot be carried out by the deconcentrated services. It also pointed out that the deconcentrated services at the regional level ensure the management of regional public services under the State, implement public policies and contribute to the development and implementation of public programs and projects at the regional level. The new charter has differentiated between the powers of the deconcentrated services at the regional level and at the prefectural or provincial level. The responsibilities of the deconcentrated services at the regional level the deconcentrated services at the regional level, as a territorial authority, have the following prerogatives

- To ensure the optimal implementation of the directives and decisions of the governmental authorities concerning the execution of governmental policy relating to the ministerial departments to which they belong;
- Ensure the execution of national and sectoral strategies adopted by the State.
- Ensure the elaboration and execution of public policies, programs and projects programmed at the regional level;
- Ensure the quality of public services provided by the public services they manage and work to guarantee their continuity;
- To supervise and direct the action of the provincial deconcentrated services under their responsibility, to ensure their proper functioning and to control their activities;
- To present any proposal or initiative likely to improve the action of the deconcentrated services and to implement public policies at the regional level;
- To present the prepositions of three-year budgetary programming concerning them and to submit them to the governmental authorities to which they belong;

Ensure the elaboration, execution and follow-up of conventions and contracts concluded for the realization of public projects and programs at the regional level;

- To take all measures likely to ensure the mutualization of the material and human means placed at their disposal;
- Drawing up the draft performance reports of the various services under their responsibility at the regional level⁴.

1.2.2. Responsibilities of the deconcentrated services at the prefectural and provincial levels

The deconcentrated services at the level of the prefecture or province, as a territorial authority, have the following prerogatives

- The exercise of the powers assigned to them by virtue of the texts in force, with regard to the activities and services provided by the public services they manage;
- The execution of directives and decisions emanating from the governmental authorities to which they report and which are communicated to them by the heads of the regional administrative representations;
- The realization of programs and projects programmed at the level of the prefecture or the province, within the limits of the attributions devolved to them.

for the realization of these missions and of the objectives provided for in the new charter, the government shall work whenever necessary to take all the measures required to revise the legislative and regulatory texts in force in order to

- Empower the deconcentrated services to exercise decision-making powers in an effective and efficient manner and to set the limits of the responsibilities entrusted to them and their areas of intervention;
- Confer the status of regional authorizing officers on the heads of deconcentrated services at the regional level in order to enable them to manage the credits allocated to the said services;
- To confer on the said chief's prerogatives relating to the management of the professional careers of the human resources under their authority at the regional and provincial levels;
- redefine the missions devolved to the central administrations concerned with regard to the attributions to be transferred to the deconcentrated services under their authority in accordance with the provisions of articles 15 and 16 of the administrative deconcentrating charter⁵.

In the same sense, the new charter of administrative deconcentrating stipulates that the central administrations must take the necessary measures to provide the deconcentrated services that

⁴ Article 15 of Decree No. 2-17-618 on the national charter for administrative deconcentrating

⁵ Article 16 of Decree No. 2-17-618 on the national charter for administrative deconcentration

are attached to them with the prerogatives that allow them to devise solutions likely to improve the public services provided by the said services to users. The Walis of the regions and the Governors of the provinces and prefectures supervise the exercise of the functions of these services.

The charter also emphasized that "the government authorities shall draw up master plans for administrative deconcentration³³ of the deconcentrated services under their authority." The purpose of this plan is to determine the powers to be transferred to the deconcentrated services (of a decision-making or delegated nature), as well as the human and financial resources that will enable them to carry out these powers, and then the objectives to be achieved by the deconcentrated services of the State and the indicators for measuring their performance in achieving these objectives. The government authorities must also evaluate the action of the deconcentrated services.

1.2.3. Good governance of relations between the deconcentrated services and the Walis and Governors

Good administrative governance implies permanent coordination of deconcentrated services by Walis and Governors (I), while relying on the mechanisms put in place for this purpose (II). In accordance with the provisions of Article 145 of the Constitution, the Walis of regions and the Governors of prefectures and provinces coordinate, under the authority of the ministers concerned, the activities of the decentralized services and ensure their proper functioning. To this end, the Walis and Governors are responsible for

- Supervising the development of programs and projects decided by the public authorities, ensuring their convergence, coherence and harmony;
 - The control of the deconcentrated services of the State, in order to ensure the execution of their missions, their obligation and these programs and projects mentioned above;
 - To conclude conventions and contracts concerning the programs and projects mentioned in the first paragraph of the first section of the second chapter of the first part of this work;
- To take all necessary measures to ensure the support, by the decentralized services of the State, of the local authorities in the realization of their development programs and projects;
- To propose to the concerned governmental authorities to take any measure of a legal, financial, administrative, technical or environmental nature falling within their competence, likely to improve the action of the deconcentrated services, in order to meet the expectations of the citizens;

- To regularly inform the concerned governmental authorities of the measures taken for the execution of the investment programs and equipment works that the State carries out in their territories, and to give their observations and proposals that can alleviate the difficulties hindering the realization of these projects within the given deadlines⁶.

2. The new coordination mechanisms according to the new charter of administrative deconcentrating

With regard to the governance guaranteed by the charter, the decree refers for the coordination of the functions of the regions to the ministerial committee, which will be chaired personally by the Head of Government. As a governance mechanism, the purpose of this committee is to develop programs and strategies to implement the provisions of the charter, to evaluate its implementation and suggest anything that can be developed on the ground, and this is what we will address in the first point. This concept is based on a new approach with integrated dimensions aimed at examining the roles and functions of the most important actors at the level of the region and this is what we will discuss in the second point of this paragraph.

2.1. Governance mechanisms

In support of the coordination policy and in order to facilitate the mission of the Wali and the Governor, the new charter came with several mechanisms to strengthen the coordination function at the territorial level and to ensure the conditions of effectiveness and efficiency in its implementation, though.

The improvement of the governance and evaluation mechanisms that were among the objectives of the decree by creating in parallel committees whose main objective is to guarantee the launch of this charter.

Practical mechanisms have therefore been put in place to ensure continuous monitoring and evaluation of this charter at all levels through.

2.1.1. The inter-ministerial commission for administrative deconcentrating

The creation of "an inter-ministerial commission for administrative deconcentrating" responsible for proposing the necessary measures to implement the general orientations of the State's policy in the field of administrative deconcentrating, and for monitoring its

⁶ Article 29 of Decree No. 2-17-618 on the national charter for administrative deconcentrating.

implementation and evaluating its results. This commission undertakes to perform the following tasks:

- Propose the creation of joint administrative representations between two or more ministerial sectors at the regional level and at the prefecture or province level
- Propose all measures aimed at improving the performance of the deconcentrated services of the State;
- To elaborate the master plans of administrative deconcentrating provided for in article 20 of the decree;
- Evaluate the policy of administrative deconcentrating and its results, and suggest any action that could develop it⁷.

This inter-ministerial commission, chaired by the Head of Government, is composed of the following members

- The government authority in charge of the Interior ;
- The Secretary General of the Government;
- The government authority in charge of finance;
- The government authority in charge of the reform of the administration and the civil service;
- Any other government authority concerned by the items on the committee's agenda.

The chairman may invite to participate in an advisory capacity, any natural or legal person whose participation he or she considers useful.

The commission shall meet at the invitation of its chairman whenever necessary and at least once every three months⁸.

All governmental authorities are required to submit to the Inter-ministerial Commission on Administrative Deconcentrating, before the end of each year, a detailed report containing the following data

- The attributions transferred, for the current year, to the deconcentrated services of the State under their authority;
- A descriptive table on the distribution of human resources between the central administrations and the decentralized State services under their authority at the regional, prefectural and provincial levels;
- The measures proposed to strengthen the policy of administrative deconcentrating⁹.

⁷ Article 38 of the charter of administrative deconcentrating

⁸ Article 41 de la charte de la déconcentration administrative.

⁹ Article 39 of the charter of administrative deconcentrating.

2.1.2. The Regional Coordinating Committee

A regional committee has been created under the Wali called "Regional Coordination Committee" whose objective is to assist him in the exercise of the tasks entrusted to him under Article 30 of the Decree of Administrative Deconcentrating in the field of coordination of the activities of the deconcentrated services of the State and public institutions that carry out their functions at the level of the region and also to ensure their proper functioning. The role of this committee is to ensure harmony between the various deconcentrated services at the level of the region, to adopt a proactive approach, to ensure consistency between public policies, programs and projects on the one hand and regional development programs on the other, and finally to simplify the procedures for access to public services provided by the deconcentrated services. This committee is chaired by the Wali of the region and includes the following members¹⁰

- The Governors of the prefectures and provinces within the region's territorial jurisdiction;
- The Secretary General of Regional Affairs;
- The heads of the deconcentrated services in the region;
- The heads of the regional investment centre's;
- The regional heads of the public services concerned¹¹.
- The General Secretariat of Regional Affairs

The establishment of an administrative structure called "Secretariat General of Regional Affairs" chaired by a Secretary General of Regional Affairs. Which in addition to the missions entrusted to him by the Wali of the region¹², is responsible for carrying out the actions of coordination, monitoring and support required to assist the Wali of the region in the exercise of its powers, to prepare the meetings of the Regional Coordination Committee, to ensure its organization, coordinate the work and establish the minutes¹³.

2.1.3. The evaluation mechanism

In order to ensure a permanent follow-up of the different stages of the implementation of the administrative deconcentrating charter, the decree mentioned a series of reports:

¹⁰ EL KHALIFI OMAR, JALLAL NOUREDDINE, & MRHIZOU HAFID. (2023). Governance of the national initiative for human development, the challenges of advanced regionalization and the requirements of administrative deconcentrating in Morocco. *International Journal of Applied Management And Economics*, 2(04), 115–166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8434363>

¹¹ Article 33 of the charter of administrative deconcentrating

¹² Article 41 of the charter of administrative deconcentrating.

¹³ Article 33 of the charter of administrative deconcentrating

The preparation of periodic reports on the results of the implementation of public and sectoral policies at the regional level. The regional coordination committee meets at the invitation of the Wali of the region whenever necessary and at least once a month, to evaluate the results of the implementation of public programs and projects that are completed at the level of the region, the results of this evaluation are submitted to the competent government authorities. This committee may meet at the request of a government authority to study the periodic reports prepared by the deconcentrated services on the implementation of programs and projects. Similarly, the General Secretariat for Regional Affairs prepares periodic reports on the results of the implementation of public and sectoral policies at the level of the region in coordination with the deconcentrated services of the State and the public institutions and bodies performing their functions at the level of the region. The General Secretariat also prepares an annual report of the regional coordination committee which will be sent by the Wali of the region, after its approval by the committee, to the inter-ministerial commission of administrative deconcentrating before the end of March of each year. These reports allow for an evaluation of the policy of administrative deconcentrating at the national level, by the inter-ministerial commission of administrative deconcentrating, from which emerge proposals for measures and procedures to be taken for its development.

Finally, the government will take all the necessary measures to review the national legal system in order to ensure its adequacy with the objectives of the charter, and it will adopt the principle of progressive application in a coherent and rational manner, taking into account the specificities and particular roles of the different deconcentrated sectors.

2.1.4 The Region, the ideal territorial space for administrative deconcentrating

Morocco implemented a regionalization reform in 2015. This reform was conceived as a new model of economic and social development that establishes the Region as the relevant framework for the deployment of territorial policies. In 2010, the Consultative Commission on Regionalization (CCR) was established by King Mohammed VI, to propose a regionalization project as a prelude to a profound reform of the structures of the State, through the determined and gradual conduct of processes of consistent and effective decentralization and deconcentrating, extensive democratization, accelerated development, social, political and administrative modernization of the country and good governance. Morocco has embarked on the effective implementation of advanced regionalization with the transfer of powers and financial and human resources to the elected presidents of the regional, provincial and

prefectural councils, which were previously the responsibility of the Walis and Governors. The importance of this relationship lies in the missions of the Walis and Governors as representatives of the central authority, in the coordination of the activities of the deconcentrated services in order to ensure their proper functioning. The Walis and Governors also ensure the preparation of the programs and projects that we have already discussed, and ensure their coherence and harmony. They can take all necessary measures to ensure that the deconcentrated services of the State implement the tasks and obligations entrusted to them in order to carry out the programs and projects in progress. The Walis and Governors may propose to the relevant government authorities to take all measures of a legal, financial or administrative nature to improve the work of the activities of the deconcentrated services at the regional, prefectural or provincial level, in order to meet the expectations of the citizens, and to simplify the procedures for their use of the services provided, In order to accompany the Governor in the exercise of the missions entrusted to him in the coordination of the activities of the deconcentrated services of the State and public institutions that perform their functions at the level of its territory, a technical committee has been created under the provisions of Chapter 5 of the Charter, this committee ensures the following tasks:

-To take all necessary measures to ensure the coordination of the deconcentrated services of the State at the level of the prefecture or the province and to ensure the continuity of the public services provided;

-Monitor planned investment projects and capital works at the prefecture or province level, and propose measures to overcome any difficulties that may be encountered;

Monitor the implementation of public and sectoral policies in the prefecture or province;

-To propose all measures aimed at improving the quality of public services provided to citizens;

- To give its opinion on the draft conventions and contracts mentioned in article 23 of the decree, relating to programs and projects within the framework of the public policies of the State or one of its branches, according to the objectives, formalities and deadlines determined;

- To examine any question falling within its competence;

- To propose recommendations for the creation of a deconcentrated service of a particular ministerial sector or between two or more sectors in the prefecture or province.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that deconcentrating in Morocco is a necessity and not an end in itself. The implementation of this process has been plagued by a series of problems that have delayed its implementation and smooth functioning. All these factors have pushed the State to review its deconcentrating model and the speed of its implementation, hence the advent of the new administrative deconcentrating charter. The latter is designed to achieve two fundamental objectives, the first is related to the problems associated with administrative infrastructure and the second is the implementation and support of advanced regionalization.

In order to achieve the objective of the correct implementation of the New Charter of Administrative deconcentrating and this within the timeframe dictated by this charter, which is three years, we give the following suggestions can be made:

- Give precise deadlines to be observed, to each ministerial department to adopt the application texts that concern it with the aim of implementing the provisions of the national charter of administrative deconcentrating;
- Evaluate the progress of the implementation of the said charter by the different stakeholders, each one in what concerns him in order to elaborate a balance sheet of achievements by calculating rates of achievement of objective (TRO) ;
- Evaluate the impact and level of achievement of the desired objectives of said charter and ideally, conduct an external impact study which is unequivocally required ;
- Involve the different departments of the State, the local authorities and the organizations that come under them, as well as any State organization with territorial competence, each in its own area of competence.

each in its own area of responsibility, to successfully implement the said charter;

- Give the Walis of regions, and the Governors of prefectures and provinces the human and material means necessary to ensure better coordination between the various deconcentrated services of the State and to play the role that was entrusted to them, namely the accompaniment;
- Request the opinion of regional and provincial authorities before the implementation of any public policy, program or project of the State because we believe that these authorities are better placed to give an opinion on the territory and the opportunity to carry out or not a given project;
- Inform the Walis of regions, and the governors of prefectures and provinces of the results of studies carried out by the deconcentrated services under their jurisdiction at

the same time as their central administrations, to enable them to give their opinions at the appropriate time;

- Make the national charter for administrative deconcentrating in correlation with the advanced regionalization project a roadmap for strengthening the regional dimension of public action and guaranteeing the proximity of essential public services to users;
- Adopt an information system based on new information and communication technologies (NICT), the example of the Province of Berkane can be a case study;
- Create coordination and monitoring committees at the level of each deconcentrated service to monitor projects and programs at the regional, prefectural or provincial level;
- Modernize the system of communication and interaction between central and deconcentrated services by adopting a contractual policy and modern techniques of management, supervision, control and evaluation taking into consideration the objectives of the charter of administrative deconcentrating;
- Create at the level of the regions, prefectures and provinces control and inspection services enabling the walis and governors to control and verify the administrative, technical and accounting management of the deconcentrated services.
- Similarly, good coordination between the deconcentrated services and the local authorities must be ensured.

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